

Effect of neem leaf application on nitrogen efficiency in lowland rice

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A field experiment on the Coimbatore lowland farm in 1984–85 wet (Jun-Sep) and dry (Oct–Feb) seasons studied the effect of neem *Azadirachta indica* L. leaf on N efficiency. Short-duration IR50 rice was planted in a clay loam (Typic Haplustalf) with low available N, medium available P, and high available K. We evaluated prilled urea (PU), neem cake-coated urea (20% urea by weight) (NCU), fresh neem leaf (FNL) at 5 t/ha and dry neem leaf (DNL) at 1.25 t/ha, each with 50, 75, and 100 kg N/ha applied basally. Fresh pongam (*Pongamia glabra* Vent) leaf (PL) at 4 t/ha substituted for FNL in the dry season. All plots received 22 kg P and 42 kg K/ha. The leaves were incorporated in the respective treatment plots 1 wk before planting.

Soil samples collected 5, 10, 20, and 30 d after planting were analyzed for $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$. FNL conserved more N in the form of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (15 ppm) in wet season (Table 1). Neem cake conserved appreciable N as $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (16 ppm) in dry season. PL had little effect on $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content (11 ppm) and hence on nitrification rate in the soil. In both seasons, leaf or cake neem plots had lower $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ than untreated urea plots. Neem products probably inhibited nitrifying organisms.

FNL produced higher grain yields in both seasons, followed closely by DNL in wet season and PL in dry season

Table 1. Effect of neem leaf application on $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ content of lowland soil.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^b	$\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (ppm)		$\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ (ppm)	
	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season
PU - N50	11	8	16	10
PU - N75	12	14	12	12
PU - N100	9	17	12	12
NCU - N50	15	13	10	7
NCU - N75	13	17	11	7
NCU - N100	13	18	11	9
FNL - N50	17	12	12	7
FNL - N75	14	15	11	8
FNL - N100	14	16	11	8
DNL - N50	14	13	11	10
DNL - N75	13	16	14	7
DNL - N100	15	15	15	7
PL - N50	–	11	–	7
PL - N75	–	11	–	6
PL - N100	–	12	–	5
CD (P = 0.05)	2	2	5	2

^aMean values of 4 soil sample analyses. ^bPU = prilled urea, NCU = neem cake urea, FNL = fresh neem leaf, DNL = dry neem leaf, PL = pongam leaf. 50, 75, and 100 indicate kilograms N/ha.

Table 2. Neem leaf fertilizer and N recovery, response, and grain yield. Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^a	N recovery percentage		N response ratio		Grain yield (t/ha)		Net return (\$/ha)	
	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry
PU - N50	59	42	16	14	4.2	3.9	218	163
PU - N75	44	40	14	11	5.0	4.0	312	170
PU - N100	32	32	15	10	5.5	4.1	360	177
NCU - N50	65	69	37	29	5.5	4.6	374	265
NCU - N75	44	35	32	13	6.1	4.1	420	174
NCU - N100	38	30	31	13	6.7	4.5	504	202
FNL - N50	67	75	53	42	6.3	5.3	478	362
FNL - N75	51	52	45	32	7.0	5.6	555	365
FNL - N100	47	48	37	22	7.3	5.4	599	340
DNL - N50	61	59	48	30	6.1	4.7	607	248
DNL - N75	51	51	46	27	7.1	5.2	572	319
DNL - N100	41	38	29	14	6.5	4.6	488	236
PL - N50	–	72	–	38	–	5.1	–	316
PL - N75	–	53	–	19	–	4.6	–	247
PL - N100	–	52	–	22	–	5.4	–	353
Control	–	–	–	–	3.7	3.2	161	83
CD (P = 0.05)	–	–	–	–	1.0	0.8	167	105

^a50, 75, and 100 indicate kilograms N/ha.

(Table 2). In both seasons, FNL recorded higher N recovery and N

response ratio. Neem leaf application also resulted in higher net returns. □

Effect of sunlight and temperature on azolla nitrogen requirements

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In North China, Azolla (Filicales Lamk) is used as livestock and poultry feed. We have found that Azolla in manure water has different $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$

requirements in winter. In summer, with high temperature and sunlight, Azolla growing in dense stinking pond water is emerald green. But in the greenhouse in winter and in the propagating tent in spring, temperatures are low and sunlight scarce. If $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in the water is over 4 ppm, Azolla gradually dies. This leads

to failure to propagate in spring and failure to survive over winter.

We measured water temperature in the pond at 5–8 cm deep at 1 day hour and 1 night hour to calculate average temperature. A ZF-2 was used to measure sunlight. $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ ppm density was measured on the 2d and last day of spring and winter periods. Changes

in Azolla color, multiplication, and death rate were calculated.

In summer, when water temperature rose to 28-30 °C with 100,000 lux and NH₄-N was 4-7 ppm, Azolla grew well. When NH₄-N was above 8 ppm, Azolla died. Azolla needed less NH₄-N at low temperatures and sunlight. In the spring propagating tent and winter greenhouse, Azolla died when NH₄-N was 4-5 ppm. It grew well when NH₄-N was 0.5-2 ppm in the winter greenhouse and 2-3 ppm in the spring propagating tent. □

Growth of azolla at different air temperatures, sunlight hours, and NH₄-N levels in Hebei, China.

Place	Hours Sunlight	Light force (Lux)	Av temp (°C)	NH ₄ -N ppm	Azolla condition
WPH ^a	5	0.05	7	3-4	Slowly died
WPH	7	0.5	15	4-5	Slowly died
NTH	7	0.5	15	3-4	Retarded growth
WPH	7	1	10	0.5-1.5	Good growth
SPT ^b	7	1	15	0.5-2	Good growth
SPT	8	0.8	10	5-7	Died
SPT	8	0.8	15	4-5	Quickly died
SPT	10	1	20	5-6	Quickly died
SPT	10	2	23	2-3	Good growth
SGP ^c	12	10	30	6-7	Good growth
SGP	12	10	30	8-12	Died
SGP	12	10	28	4-6	Good growth

^aWinter-passing house. ^bSpring propagating tent. ^cSummer growing pond.

Response of rice to *Azospirillum* inoculation

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Table 1. Effect of *Azospirillum* seed inoculation on seed germination and vigor index. Coimbatore, India.

<i>Azospirillum</i> isolate	Germination (%)	Vigor index	Increase (%)
	<i>CO 40</i>		
Sp. 7	92.0	1140	16.3
IPI	96.0	1680	71.4
S-3	94.0	1480	51.0
Untreated control	86.0	980	-
CD (P=0.05)	4.8	180	
	<i>IR50</i>		
sp. 7	97.0	1380	27.7
IPI	96.0	1440	33.3
S-3	92.0	1260	16.6
Untreated control	88.0	1080	-
CD (P=0.05)	3.2	148	

We studied the influence of inoculating seed of IR50 and Co 40 rice varieties with three strains of nitrogen-fixing bacterium *Azospirillum brasilense*: Sp. 7, Brazil; IPI isolated from root tissues of *Ipomoea* sp., India; and nonnitrogen-fixing *A. brasilense* mutant S-3, University of Florida, USA.

Seeds of IR50 and Co 40 were surface sterilized by soaking in sterile water for 12 h, separately inoculated with broth cultures of the bacterium strains, and dried in the shade. Each seed surface had an average 2.2×10^5 cells of the bacterium. The seeds were germinated at 30°C (paper towel method). Vigor index (shoot length + root length × % germination) was determined at 5 d.

In another experiment, inoculated seeds were sown in pots containing wet field soil. At 30 d after seeding,

seedling weight, root biomass, number of roots, and plant height were recorded.

Seed inoculation significantly increased germination and vigor index of both cultivars (Table 1).

In general, all three strains of *Azospirillum* enhanced seedling vigor. Shoot and root development, number of primary and secondary roots formed, and seedling weight increased significantly. Response was higher with IPI (Table 2).

Inoculation with S-3 also had positive effects. All three strains produced appreciable amounts of phytohormones *in vitro*, notably indoleacetic acid and gibberellic acid. This suggests that initial growth responses to inoculation might be due more to the secretion of growth-promoting substances than to biological N fixation. □

Table 2. Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on growth of 2 rice varieties.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	CO 40				IR50			
	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Primary roots (no.)	Dry wt (mg) of seedling	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Primary roots (no.)	Dry wt (mg) of seedling
<i>Azospirillum</i> (Sp. 7)	16.34 a	6.20 a	5.80 a	74.0 ab	14.26 bc	5.80 bc	5.60 b	92.0 b
<i>Azospirillum</i> (IPI)	17.26 a	5.80 ab	5.33 a	80.0 a	18.20 a	6.48 c	6.90 a	112.0 a
<i>Azospirillum</i> (S-3)	16.20 a	5.20 b	5.20 a	68.0 b	19.20 a	5.40 a	4.20 cd	96.0 b
Uninoculated control	11.60 b	4.70 c	4.30 b	60.0 c	12.21 c	5.00 a	3.60 d	86.0 b
CD (P = 0.05)	2.27	0.69	0.81	6.7	2.26	0.76	0.93	10.9

^aFigures followed by the same letters are statistically similar.